

THE ROLE OF LANGUAGE IN IDENTITY FORMATION

Hayitmurodova Gulnur Zafarovna

gulinurhayitmurodova162@gmail.com

Faculty of English Philology, Uzbekistan State

Word Languages University,

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

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Annotation: This article gives information about how new language learning can influence on individual's perception of the world and their understanding of self. It also explores the potential for language learning to broaden perspectives, increase empathy, and enhance cultural understanding. The article analyses how language can be a tool for promoting inclusivity, diversity and social justice.

Key words: language learning, new languages, identity, personality, cultures, different nationalities, social movements.

Language is one of the greatest discoveries in the history of mankind, without which humans would be no different from animals. It is the main means of communication that unites society and countries, as well as a unique element that expresses people's mutual thoughts, feelings, and inner experiences. At the same time, language is a tool that transmits knowledge accumulated over centuries from generation to generation. The language of each country has its own history, and it is not for nothing that it is said to be a factor in the formation of personality. Language is considered as the main tool for determining a country's position in the world, moreover, its culture, the spirit and mood of that language will be absorbed into a person through it. If we pay attention, the behavior of each nation, tone of speech, expression of thoughts are different, they are not similar to each other, sometimes their way of life may seem strange to us. In fact, this is a normal situation, along with the language, a person's identity is formed.

Today, most people around the world are not limited to one or two languages, but are multilingual and are discovering new worlds for themselves. It is said that a person who has learned many languages has a broad mind because the language has taught them to think globally and opened many doors of knowledge. But one thing should always be kept in mind, when a new language enters a country, its culture also enters directly. When a person learns another language, he inevitably learns its culture, which in turn affects the formation of his personality. There are several positive effects of language

learning on personality. Firstly, people are exposed to diverse cultures, traditions, and ways of thinking while they learn a new language. When learning another language, a person reads books written in that language, shows interest in its history, watches movies, regularly follows the news, during these processes he automatically learns the customs of that nation, the behavior of its people, as a result, he can communicate with representatives of the nation without any misunderstandings and this will help to improve inter-ethnic relations. Secondly, it strengthens self-awareness. As a person navigates a new language and culture, he becomes more aware of his own cultural biases, assumptions, and communication styles. People gain a deeper understanding of how their own language shapes their perception of the world and how they interact with others. This self-reflection can lead to personal growth and a greater appreciation for person's own identity.

Language is not just a tool for communication, but also cornerstone, powerful shaper of identity. Among the many symbolic resources available for the cultural production of identity, language is the most flexible and pervasive. Using survey data from Catalonia and exploiting variation in the number of years of compulsory education under Catalan instruction, results show that individuals who experienced greater exposure to teaching in Catalan are more likely to say that they feel more Catalan than Spanish. As is the case for most of the reforms involving changes in the languages of instruction, the introduction of bilingualism in Catalan schools was associated with other adjustments in the educational system, such as changes in textbooks and course contents. [2]. By this example it is obvious that new language is new feelings, new personality, they start to feel, think even dream in that language. Therefore, it is important to teach, learn new languages attentively and carefully so that they could not impact on our personality, identity negatively, otherwise, it would be difficult to give up the behaviour they formed.

A person's identity can be influenced by different factors (parents, peers, region) at different ages. These factors can influence a person's language use:

- During childhood, a person's language will mirror their parents' as they are who they'll interact with the most.
- When speakers reach secondary school, they may start to adopt their peers' language features due to socialising with more social groups.
- A person's regional identity will be shown through their use of a regional accent. This could change to take on features of different regions, for example, if someone moves to a different area for a significant length of time.[1]

In 1999, linguists Keith and Shuttleworth carried out a series of conversation analyses of men's and women's speech. Their findings concluded that there are typical speech characteristics for each gender, shown in the table below [3]:

Women	Men
● Talk too much	● Insult each other
● More polite	● Competitive in conversation
● Hesitant	● Dominate conversation
● Complain or nag	● Speak with authority
● Ask questions	● Give more commands
● Support each other	● Interrupt more

From this table it can be concluded two genders have two different speaking styles associated not only with language, but also with identity and individuality.

In conclusion, the language as a social interactional tool plays a crucial role to shape the cultural identity representing and framing people's linguistic and cultural backgrounds to exchange their personal experiences, social realities, cultural norms and historical traditions among the members of a specific group establishing an enriched socio-cultural life within a country. [4]

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